

‘Guardians of the Sacred’ and ‘Stewards of God’s Mysteries’

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Abstract

The liturgy, especially the celebration of the Eucharist is the most effective means of sanctification, of the celebration of the Church’s faith, and of transmitting the faith. Together with sacred Scripture and the Fathers of the Church, it is a living source of authentic and sound spirituality. The Eucharistic celebration should make us to become more Eucharistic in life, motivates and energizes us for effective ministry. The Synodal life of the Church finds its finest expression in the Eucharistic celebration through shared liturgical action of the faithful (*Instrumentum Laboris* of 2023 Synod, no. 47). Hence, “*Ars Celebrandi*,”- the art / manner of celebrating - is of paramount importance for making liturgy meaningful and fruitful, and every effort has to be made to celebrate it in a dignified manner. This, in turn, requires proper biblical and liturgical formation of all in the spirit of the liturgy.

Introduction

When the great Bible Scholar late Cardinal Carlo Maria Martini of Milan was asked the question, ‘What is the Church for?’, his answer was: To ensure that *the Truth of the Word of God* is proclaimed, and to ensure that *true worship of God takes place in the liturgy*. The renowned theologian Henri de Lubac stated the following: “The Church makes the Eucharist and the Eucharist makes the Church.” These observations emphasize that to facilitate genuine God / Christ experience through meaningful proclamation of the Word, and worthy and fruitful celebration of the Sacraments, especially the *Eucharist*, is the *core of priestly ministry*.

1. Liturgy and Life

Pope John Paul II reminds us that liturgy, especially the celebration of the Eucharist ‘is the most effective means of sanctification, of the celebration of

the Church's faith, and of transmitting the faith. Together with sacred Scripture and the Fathers of the Church, it is a living source of authentic and sound spirituality' (*Ecclesia in Europa*, no. 70). The Eucharist also motivates and energizes the faithful to effective ministry, as called for in the rite of conclusion: 'Go you are sent forth.' The faithful are called upon to share what they have experienced during the celebration. Pope Benedict XVI stated that "the wonder we experience at the gift God has made to us in Christ gives new impulse to our lives and commits us to becoming witnesses of his love" (*Sacramentum caritatis*, no. 85).

2. 'Ars celebrandi'

"Let the Parish Priest (and other priests too) strive so that the Most Holy Eucharist will be the centre of the parish congregation, and let him ensure that Christ's faithful are nourished through it" (*Redemptionis Sacramentum*, no.32). Hence, "*Ars Celebrandi*,"- the art / manner of celebrating - is of paramount importance for making liturgy meaningful and fruitful. True spiritual experience and passing it down to other people are the key elements. Pope Benedict XVI states that in the beauty of celebrating the Eucharist "the splendour of God's glory surpasses all worldly beauty. The truest beauty is the love of God which is revealed to us in the paschal mystery" (*Sacramentum caritatis*, no. 35). Pope John Paul II affirmed that the Eucharist is a mystery and that every effort has to be made to celebrate it "in a dignified manner by every community..." (*Mane nobiscum Domine*, no. 17).

The Eucharistic celebration reveals the authenticity of the life and faith of the believers, and most importantly, the actions of the Holy Spirit. Thus, the liturgy is not simply a cultic act, but proclaims "the beauty of God that can be experienced, touches our heart and changes our life" (*Directory of Catechesis*, no. 175). Liturgy should be understood more with the heart, with internal openness to an 'encounter with the One to come.'

The *ars celebrandi* includes the entire ambient (*words, gestures, postures, liturgical vestments, sacred vessels and art, etc.*). Hymns and chants (of the psalms) too express the sense of the sacred and correspond with the nature of the celebration, while respecting the liturgical regulations (*Sacramentum caritatis*, nos. 40–42). Some differences of opinion may arise: For example, traditional Church (sacred) music or modern praise and worship music and songs. There are many ways to experience and to express the One Faith.

3. Renewal of the Liturgy of the Word of God

The Constitution *Sacrosanctum Concilium* states that Christ “is present in His word, since it is He Himself who speaks when the Holy Scriptures are read in the Church” (*SC*, no. 7; *Verbum Domini*, no. 56). The Apostolic Exhortation *Verbum Domini* continues: “The liturgy of the Word and the Eucharistic liturgy, are so closely connected with each other that they form but ONE single worship” (no. 56). The Constitution *Dei Verbum* had already affirmed this co-relationship: “The Church has always venerated the divine Scriptures just as she venerated the Body of the Lord, insofar as she never she never ceases, particularly in the sacred liturgy, to partake of the bread of life and offer it to the faithful from the ONE table of the Word of God and the Body of Christ” (no. 21). The image of the ONE table emphasizes the inseparability of Word and Sacrament which together nourish the people of God. The Decree on the Ministry and Life of Priests (*PO*, no. 4) makes clear two points: (a) The people of God *is formed and lives by the Word of God* (cf. Mt 4:4; Jn 6:68; 1 Pet 1:23), and (b) they should *receive it from their priests*, especially at the Eucharistic celebration.

At the beginning of the solemn Mass, ‘the Book of the Gospels’ (*Evangelary*) is carried in procession and placed on the altar in order to indicate the *presence of the Word of God* from the very beginning of the Mass; again from the altar it is taken for the liturgical proclamation. Thus, liturgy offers “space” for the Word of God. This is, then, *the sacramental horizon* of divine Revelation or ‘*sacramentality of the Word.*’

The proclaimed Word has more a *performative* – “the Word is alive and active” (cf. Heb 4:12) *and transformative function*. The proclaimed Word is fulfilled when it *encounters* the hearers, *and the function of the homily is to make this encounter a “real meeting / dialogue between the faithful and God”* (*Dies Domini*, no. 41), *as possible here and now – a salvific ‘today’* (cf. Lk 4:21; 19:9; 23:43) - *and to put fire into his hearers’ heart* (cf. Lk 24:13-32). In this way, the homily becomes “*an act of worship...*” (*Homiletic directory*, no. 4), and preparing to preach a homily ‘becomes an act of prayer’ – “I preach in order to pray” (Rabbi Abraham Heschel).

4. Eucharist and Catechesis

The Eucharistic liturgy is “the privileged place for catechizing the People of God” (*CCC*, no. 1074). Further, ‘it is one of the primary and indispensable sources of the Church’s catechesis, mainly because the contents, language, gestures and words of faith belong to each other in the very act of

faith' (*Directory*, no. 95). A special dimension Eucharistic liturgy is *mystagogical catechesis*. It includes "explanation of the *rites* in the light of the redemptive events, or introduction into the meaning of liturgical *signs and gestures...*" (*Directory*, no. 98), enabling "the faithful to enter more deeply into *the mystery being celebrated*" (*Sacramentum caritatis*, no. 64). *Prescribed gestures and postures* are important as they are bodily expressions of reverence. It also educates them to look at the Eucharistic celebration in relation to their life, making it a *real source of spirituality, prayer and life*. In this way, the Eucharistic *celebration will be at the centre of their lives*.

Introductions and commentaries at certain important moments in the Eucharistic celebration can be very helpful. Of all them, *introduction to the liturgy of the Word* seems particularly useful "to *focus the attention of the faithful, to listen to and accept the Word of God* in a spirit of communion with the Church and with a clear awareness of its unity with the Eucharist" (*Sacramentum caritatis*, no. 45).

5. Eucharistic Celebration as Testimony to the "sense of the Sacred"

A story about the beginning of Christianity in Russia says that King Vladimir was not convinced by the arguments presented by representatives of Islam or Judaism or Papal envoys about their faith. The key to his conversion to Christian faith (in the Byzantine form) was the account given by his messengers, who were stunned by the beauty and dignity of the Easter services at *Hagia Sophia* Church in Constantinople. They said: "We knew not whether we were in heaven or on earth, for surely there is no such splendour or beauty anywhere upon earth. We cannot describe it to you. Only we know that God dwells there among men and that their service surpasses the worship of all other places. We cannot forget that beauty."

We need to recapture the '*sense of the sacred*' because of the *evangelizing power of our liturgical celebrations*. Pope Benedict XVI says 'though its purpose is primarily to worship God, and sanctify the participants, the Eucharistic celebration is undoubtedly a *testimony of faith*. It shows to the world the *primacy of God* in the world.'

Correct and inspiring celebration of the Eucharist puts God in people's lives. For Christians, it is a possibility to *grow into Christ*, and for others (other Christians, etc.), this *testimony of faith* may help them to open up to the Gospel. The celebration must *be integrated in the whole life of the Church*. "The effectiveness of liturgical actions consists in the *ever deeper*

insight into the Word of God and the Mystery which Jesus celebrated” (Third Instruction for the Implementation of Sacrosanctum Concilium, no.1).

The *Church architecture as a whole, the interior and the sanctuary* in particular, are the best expressions of the *sense of the sacred*. They should offer *space for spiritual experience*. A *well-designed and properly-positioned altar and the ambo emphasize the significance of the Word and the Sacrament, and their inter-relationship* (VD, no. 68). *The place of the celebrant shows his pastoral mission; the right place for the Crucifix and the Tabernacle (and the lamp) directs people’s mind and senses to the presence of the Lord (General Instruction, nos. 314–15). Sacred art (pictures and statues, sacred vessels, etc.), should also be well-cared for because they witness to the Transcendent.*

6. Moments of Silence

A book (by Cardinal Robert Sarah) titled, “*The Power of Silence against the Dictatorship of Noise* is an eye-opener.” *Maintaining silence, especially interior silence* key moments in the liturgy is important. *Verbum Domini* remarks: “the Word, in fact, can only be spoken and heard in silence, outward and inward... people are afraid of detaching themselves, even for a moment, from the mass media. For this reason, it is necessary that *the People of God be educated in the value of silence...* Hence I encourage Pastors to foster *moments of recollection* whereby, with the assistance of the Holy Spirit, *the Word of God can find a welcome in our hearts*” (no. 66). However, proper instruction can ensure that the time for silence is not treated *as a break in the celebration* but as a time of *personal encounter with the Lord, for example, to initiate personal prayer.*’ The following words require our attention: *‘those who wish to follow Jesus need to imitate his stillness before they can imitate his actions; they need to understand his silence before they can speak his words’* (John M. Talbot, *The World is my Cloister*, 21-22).

7. The Christian Sunday

Sunday holds a special place in Christian life. The early Christians in North Africa, when questioned by the agents of Emperor Diocletian, responded: “Without Sunday Mass we cannot live,” which meant – if we cannot celebrate the Eucharist we cannot live, our Christian life would die.”

As Pope Benedict XVI noted, “the Christians’ customary practice of gathering on the first day after the Sabbath to celebrate the resurrection of Christ ... is also what defines the form of a life renewed by an encounter

with Christ. Sunday *commemorates the radical newness brought by Christ*. It is the day when Christians should rediscover the *Eucharistic dimension of their lives*” (*Sacramentum caritatis*, no. 72).

Keeping Sunday holy cannot be limited to participation in the Eucharist only. Sunday should be used to ‘live’ one’s faith expressed in the Eucharistic celebration – to become the Eucharist for others through works of charity and other forms of sharing the Gospel. This is particularly important in a context when Sunday is gradually losing its sacral dimension.

8. The Eucharist builds up Community

Henri De Lubac’s statement, referred to at the beginning, means a Christian community or a parish is essentially a ‘Eucharistic community.’ Hence, the Eucharistic celebration should help the participants experience that they are part of the *faith-community, both local and universal*. The fraternal encounter in the Eucharistic celebration is *not only a space for personal religious fulfilment*, but is an outstanding means *to foster and manifest what the Church, in essence, is, namely, community and communion* (cf. *SC*, no. 2). In the liturgical celebration, the faithful become *a community*, and experience its *radical unity, and also the beauty of its diversity*. Pope John Paul II noted that ‘all this will be helped by *various gestures, use of inclusive language, and by the tone of prayer, or being alert to the needs of all in the community*’ (*Dies Domini*, no. 44). This rich experience at the Eucharistic ‘can help the faithful to *better identify with the Church* and “*promote a spirituality of communion*” (*Novo millennio ineunte*, no. 43).

9. The Liturgy / Eucharistic Celebration as Synodal Experience

The *Synodal life* of the Church finds its *finest expression in the Eucharistic celebration* through shared liturgical action of the faithful (*Instrumentum Laboris* of 2023 Synod, no. 47). ‘Conscious and active participation’ (*SC*, no. 14) is, first and foremost, *an inner entering into God’s presence*, that is, ‘the participants internally joining in the Eucharistic Prayer, which is offered by the celebrant and which leads the faithful into the action of God.’ Yet, it can take place only if a person has deep personal faith and takes active part in the life of the Church because *life and liturgy are organically connected*.

The *new ministries of ‘Lector’, ‘Acolyte’ and ‘the Catechist,’* should find their place in the Eucharistic liturgy. Since the Christian faithful are “a chosen race, a royal priesthood, and a holy people” (1 Pet 2:9; 2:4-5; cf. *LG*, no.10), their active participation by taking up certain functions (*lectors*,

acolytes, cantors, commentators, etc. - cf. *SC*, no. 26) can make the synodal experience a reality. *Adult altar servers* can take up some important tasks. Putting into practice the liturgical principle, ‘wherever a *function can be shared, it is always better to do that and partake in it both more fully and fruitfully,*’ is very helpful. Those chosen for these ministries should receive *adequate training* and be given ‘*missio canonica*’ so that it is really understood as a *call– a grace* (cf. Rom 12:3; 1 Cor 3:10) – for the building up of the body of Christ (cf. Eph 4:15-16).

10. Formation in the Spirit of the Liturgy

Meaningful and fruitful celebration and participation in liturgical celebration require *proper biblical and liturgical formation of all* in the *spirit of the liturgy* (cf. *RS*, no. 170;). This would help them see the *difference between liturgy centre of spiritual life and popular piety/devotion* (cf. *SC*, no. 10). While the idea of Eucharist as a ‘banquet’ may suggest close familiarity, it can also lead to risking the fact of ‘real presence.’ The Eucharist is ‘*pre-eminently a sacrifice*’ (*RS*, no. 38). Pope Francis warns priests against ‘spiritual worldliness’ in liturgy too, in the form of ‘formalism, functionalism, etc.

11. The Celebrants

“All priests should take the trouble of properly cultivating their liturgical knowledge and ability” (*RS*, no. 33). Since ‘liturgical celebrations belong to the Church’ (cf. *SC*, no. 26), priests as ‘*guardians*’ of the “sacred” should take *utmost care to avoid ‘a casual approach,’* and never allow to *trivialize the holiest of Christian faith*’ - the Eucharistic celebration; rather we must ‘rediscover the *sense for the sacred*’ and ‘*capacity for mystery.*’ This is possible only when we are “*thoroughly imbued with the spirit and power of the liturgy,* and undertake to give instruction about it” (*SC*, no. 14). It is necessary to steadily deepen the spirit of the liturgy, *primarily to facilitate a true God experience* by dignified liturgical celebrations. Personal conviction about the sense of the sacred and the *importance of various elements of the liturgy is necessary* in order to foster its true spirit.

12. The Participants / Faithful

The introduction of the new ministries offers many opportunities for the faithful. Vatican II states that “Pastors must realize that it is their duty to ensure that the faithful take part fully aware of what they are doing, actively engaged in the rite, and enriched by its effects” (*SC*, no. 11). Authority

in the Church is to empower the laity for the building up of the Church (cf. *LG*, no. 30; Eph 4:15-16). Proper training will enable them to understand that their ministry is a gift / call from God, and not a claim to take over the functions of the clergy, and that they sanctify themselves in the exercise of their responsibilities. Further, it will help to avoid confusing the roles of the laity and the clergy. ‘*Clericalization*’ of the laity is as bad as ‘*clericalism*’ and ‘*secularization*’ of the clergy and religious

Conclusion

The Eucharistic celebration makes us more Eucharistic in life. It is like a grain, which then sprouts, grows, matures and blooms with flowers of faith, hope and good deeds especially for the benefit of the poor – moving from the flesh of Christ to the flesh of the suffering (adapted from Pope Francis, *Catechesis on the Holy Mass*, 68-69).

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